

Digital Twins for Sustainable Multimedia Delivery in 6G Edge Systems

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Abstract—Next-generation multimedia services impose extreme requirements on latency, bandwidth, and energy efficiency, pushing the network edge to become the primary node of computation and control. Meeting these demands requires a fundamental evolution of the user plane, where the User Plane Function (UPF) transitions from a static traffic anchor to a dynamic, distributed, and compute-aware orchestration point. This paper examines how Network Digital Twins (NDTs) enable this evolution by providing continuously updated, predictive models of network behavior that support the design and operation of a sustainable multimedia delivery pipeline. Through the data provided by the NDTs, operators can evaluate UPF placement strategies, dynamic scaling policies, and energy-aware routing mechanisms under realistic multimedia workloads. Through the integration of a Digital Twin (DT) in the loop, the resulting orchestration framework have the elements to compute activation, traffic steering, and path selection with both QoE constraints and energy-efficiency objectives. By integrating intelligence into the user-plane control loop, next-generation networks can support immersive and compute-intensive multimedia services while maintaining a sustainable energy footprint. The paper positions NDT and DT of Networked Devices and Network Digital Twins as a core enabler of 6G-era multimedia systems, where joint communication-compute optimization and energy-aware UPF management become essential design principles.

Index Terms—NDT, DTs, Network Digital Twin, Digital Twins of Networked Devices, Edge, 6G, 5G, Network Intelligence

I. INTRODUCTION

Next-generation multimedia services are rapidly emerging as dominant contributors to network traffic and computational demand. Applications such as immersive XR, cloud gaming, volumetric media, and holographic telepresence impose stringent requirements on bandwidth, compute availability, and end-to-end latency. As these workloads grow in scale and complexity, the network itself becomes a critical contributor of multimedia quality, not just a provider of bandwidth and also of services that support the stream transmission. Multimedia performance does only depend on media-processing

algorithms but is also shaped by how the network orchestrates compute, connectivity, and energy resources at the edge.

The emerging 6G standard focuses at introducing capabilities such as sub-millisecond latency, joint communication–compute orchestration, AI-native network control, semantic communication, and cloud-native architectures spanning a continuum from central cloud to edge nodes. At the center of this ecosystem, sustainability is emerging as a core requirement. With traffic volumes continuing to grow, it is no longer viable for energy consumption to scale proportionally. Multimedia workloads are already among the largest contributors to mobile network energy use and this aspect makes the sustainability challenge even more relevant. Ensuring that performance improvements do not come at the cost of unsustainable energy consumption growth requires intelligent orchestration mechanisms capable of aligning network behavior with energy-efficiency objectives.

To this end, 5G-Advanced and 6G standards introduce the User Plane Function (UPF) into their architectures to enable sophisticated user plane management. In this architectures, the UPF is the Network Function (NF) responsible for packet routing and forwarding, packet inspection, and QoS management towards the Data Network and the Edge, enabling a dynamic, distributed, and compute-aware approach. The positioning of the UPF, its behavior in terms of scalability, and its interaction with edge computing resources directly influence where multimedia applications are processed, how traffic is routed, the length of data paths, and the number of network functions that must remain active. Consequently, UPF orchestration becomes central to achieving both high QoE and sustainable operation.

These innovations promise unprecedented performance for multimedia services, but they also introduce new design trade-offs. Evaluating these capabilities under realistic conditions—before and after deployment—requires accurate, continuously updated models of the network. Network Digital

Twins (NDTs) provide this foundation. By maintaining a predictive, real-time representation of the network and networked devices, NDTs enable the exploration of “what-if” scenarios, the validation of architectural choices, and the optimization of multimedia delivery pipelines. They support energy-aware UPF placement, dynamic scaling policies, compute-aware routing, and QoE-driven traffic steering. Their ability to model the interplay between network load, compute activation, energy consumption, and multimedia QoE makes them a key enabler for sustainable next-generation multimedia systems.

In this context, the concept of Digital Twinning offers a powerful tool for designing and operating multimedia-centric networks. They allow operators to test UPF topologies, evaluate energy/QoE trade-offs, model renewable-energy availability at edge sites, and optimize joint communication–compute strategies. By integrating DT-driven intelligence into the user-plane control loop, next-generation networks can support demanding multimedia services while maintaining a sustainable energy footprint.

This paper investigates how DTs of Networked Devices can be leveraged to optimize multimedia delivery at the edge, focusing on their role in UPF evolution, orchestration strategies, and sustainable network operation. We show how DT-based methodologies can guide the design, validation, and optimization of 6G-era multimedia systems.

II. RELATED WORK

This section reviews prior research in three areas central to this study: Digital Twins (NDTs) in networks, edge-based multimedia delivery, and user-plane orchestration for next-generation systems. These domains collectively motivate the need for predictive, fine-grained coordination across communication and computation.

A. Characteristics of Emerging Multimedia Workloads

Modern multimedia exhibit stringent requirements on latency, bandwidth, and reliability, and, at the same time, with high variability, strong latency sensitivity, and substantial computational intensity. This fundamentally alters the relationship between multimedia processing and network operation and traditional architectures, where media quality was primarily determined by application-layer mechanisms, are not able to provide appropriate support. This shift establishes the network, and particularly the edge, as a critical locus of control for multimedia performance and sustainability. Future systems will need to rely on tightly integrated network intelligence to ensure consistent Quality of Experience (QoE). Furthermore, they must also take into account the fact that these workloads impose significant energy demands, particularly when distributed across multiple edge sites. In the absence of coordinated orchestration, the activation of edge computing resources can result in inefficient energy consumption, thereby shifting the sustainability challenge to a system-level dimension.

The following use cases underscore the need for mechanisms capable of anticipating workload dynamics, evaluating

alternative configurations, and optimizing resource usage accordingly, thereby highlighting the need for strong network support through predictive, network-aware orchestration mechanisms:

- *Cloud gaming and interactive media*: require ultra-low latency and depend on stable bidirectional flows with tight jitter bounds, motivating dynamic placement of compute and user-plane functions.
- *XR rendering offload and and holographic telepresence*: demand high bandwidth and strict latency constraints, extremely low end-to-end delay and high data rates, thus making compute-aware routing and edge selection critical.
- *Video analytics pipelines*: involve continuous ingestion of high-volume data streams, requiring efficient distribution of compute tasks across edge nodes.
- *Metaverse and multi-user virtual environments*: require synchronization across distributed users and compute resources, with stringent QoE and energy constraints.

B. Edge Computing

The increasing demand for interactive and high-resolution multimedia services has accelerated research on edge computing as a means to reduce latency and improve QoE. Surveys on mobile edge computing [1] and edge-cloud architectures [2] emphasize the importance of computation offloading, adaptive resource allocation, and energy-efficient operation. In parallel, the evolution of the 5G user plane—particularly the deployment and placement of the User Plane Function (UPF) has been studied in terms of performance trade-offs and architectural flexibility [3]. Edge-based orchestration mechanisms have also been shown to reduce energy consumption and improve service responsiveness [4]. These findings collectively demonstrate the need for dynamic, context-aware management of compute and network resources.

C. The Data Plane at the Edge: Evolving Role of the UPF

The User Plane Function (UPF) plays a central role in the evolution of the data plane. Traditionally implemented as a static forwarding element, the UPF is transitioning into a dynamic, distributed, and compute-aware component capable of adapting its placement and activation state to service requirements.

Recent surveys on mobile multimedia processing [5] and AI-driven network orchestration [6] highlight the limitations of traditional approaches and the need for predictive, adaptive control mechanisms. Dynamic UPF selection, compute-aware routing, and proactive resource activation have been proposed as key enablers for supporting these workloads. Early work on NDT-driven multimedia delivery at the edge further demonstrates the potential of integrating predictive models into the control loop to sustain performance under highly variable conditions.

It becomes clear how, in this ecosystem, the UPF behavior determines the locus of traffic processing, the extent of compute activation, the efficiency of data paths, and the number

of network functions that must remain operational. Therefore, a dynamic UPF placement enables the network to respond to real-time conditions. UPFs positioned closer to users can be activated during periods of high demand to satisfy latency constraints, whereas centralized UPFs may be preferred during low-traffic intervals to reduce energy consumption. Scaling mechanisms allow UPF instances to be instantiated or decommissioned based on predicted multimedia load, thereby reducing idle energy waste. For multimedia services, this flexibility enables selective routing of flows through the most efficient paths and supports compute-aware routing strategies that incorporate energy availability at edge sites.

D. Digital Twins of Networked Devices and Network Digital Twins

The concept of Digital Twins (DTs) originated in industrial and cyber-physical systems [7], where virtual replicas are used to monitor and predict system behavior. This paradigm has recently been extended to communication networks, enabling real-time visibility, performance forecasting, and closed-loop optimization [8], [9]. This enabled the definition of Digital Twins of Networked Devices and of Network Digital Twins.

Network Digital Twins provide a predictive, continuously updated representation of the network that supports both pre-deployment analysis and operational decision-making. Prior to deployment, NDTs enable the evaluation of architectural alternatives, including joint communication-compute orchestration strategies, dynamic user-plane placement, and energy-aware routing mechanisms. During operation, NDTs integrate live telemetry to refine their models and support real-time optimization.

Digital Twins of Networked Devices and Network Digital Twins represent a "mirror" of actual devices and networks. As such, they provide the analytical foundation required for intelligent data-plane orchestration. By modeling network state, compute load, energy consumption, and multimedia QoE, (N)DTs enable energy-aware UPF placement, dynamic scaling policies, green routing strategies, and predictive orchestration based on workload forecasts. Through these capabilities, (N)DTs transform the UPF into a programmable, energy-aware control point and make sustainable multimedia delivery feasible at scale. They ensure that next-generation networks can support demanding multimedia services while adhering to stringent energy-efficiency requirements.

For multimedia services, NDTs facilitate workload forecasting, compute activation planning, QoE-driven routing, and energy modeling across heterogeneous edge sites. Their predictive capabilities allow the network to anticipate demand fluctuations, evaluate performance–energy trade-offs, and coordinate resources accordingly. As such, NDTs serve as a foundational enabler for next-generation multimedia systems, ensuring that performance and sustainability objectives are jointly satisfied. DTs and NDTs have been proposed as a foundational component of 6G architectures, supporting tasks such as traffic prediction, network slicing, and AI-driven control [10]. These works highlight the potential of DTs/NDTs to

Fig. 1. System architecture showing the NDT placed in the closed loop

anticipate network dynamics and guide orchestration decisions in complex, heterogeneous environments. In this work, we focus our attention on Digital Twins of Networked Devices, as we use the concept of the Digital Twin applied to the hardware devices supporting edge delivery of multimedia services.

III. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

This section presents the architectural framework that enables the integration of Network Digital Twins (NDTs) into next-generation multimedia delivery systems. As shown in Fig. 1, the architecture is designed to support predictive modeling, closed-loop optimization, and sustainable orchestration across the communication–compute continuum. It consists of three tightly coupled elements: the physical network and edge infrastructure, the virtualized and programmable control plane, and the NDT-driven intelligence layer. Together, these components provide the foundation for dynamic user-plane management, energy-aware routing, and compute-aware multimedia processing.

A. Control Loop and UPF Orchestration

This section describes the control mechanisms that leverage the NDT to enable intelligent and adaptive user-plane management. The control loop operates as a closed-cycle system that continuously aligns network behavior with the performance and sustainability requirements of multimedia services.

a) Physical Infrastructure and UPF Diversity: The User Plane Function forwards user traffic between the radio access network and the data network. In edge deployments, different UPF implementations are available. Kernel-bypass dataplanes deliver high throughput and low latency but consume near-constant power regardless of load. Cloud-native, user-space instances scale their power consumption with offered traffic and can be replicated horizontally to handle demand peaks. This diversity gives the orchestrator meaningful choices: selecting the right UPF type and scale for the current traffic conditions directly affects both service quality and energy consumption.

b) Telemetry and NDT Integration: Telemetry from the network and edge infrastructure is collected through the monitoring block shown in Fig. 1 and fed into the NDT, which synthesizes this information into an updated representation

of the system state. The Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF) provides network-level indicators such as traffic load, latency, and QoS compliance. Infrastructure-level metrics, including compute utilization and energy consumption at the edge node are collected through the Management Data Analytics Function (MDAF) and the Infrastructure Data Analytics Function (IDAF). These inputs allow the NDT to maintain an up-to-date representation of the system and to generate the forecasts that inform orchestration decisions. By maintaining this representation continuously, the NDT also supports what-if evaluation of alternative UPF configurations and routing strategies before any change is committed to the live network.

c) Actuation and Feedback: Based on the NDT’s assessment, the NF Orchestrator adjusts the active UPF configuration at each control period, aligned with the NWDAF reporting interval. The orchestrator may trigger UPF instantiation, migration, consolidation, or deactivation to maintain optimal operation. The outcome of each actuation is captured by the monitoring functions and fed back into the NDT, closing the control loop. This continuous feedback process ensures that the network remains responsive to workload fluctuations and evolving service requirements.

B. Role in Sustainable Operation

Sustainability is a central design objective of the proposed system, and the NDT plays a pivotal role in achieving it. By modeling the energy consumption of network and compute resources, the NDT enables the orchestrator to identify configurations that minimize power usage while maintaining acceptable QoE. This includes consolidating UPF instances during low-demand periods, steering traffic toward energy-efficient paths, and exploiting renewable-energy availability at specific edge sites.

Through its predictive and analytical capabilities, the NDT ensures that sustainability considerations are embedded directly into the control loop rather than treated as an afterthought. As a result, the network can support demanding multimedia services while adhering to stringent energy-efficiency requirements.

IV. BUILDING THE DIGITAL TWIN OF NETWORKED DEVICES

The Digital Twin of Networked Devices (DT) constitutes the intelligence layer of the proposed architecture. It provides a continuously updated, high-fidelity representation of the operational network or appliances, capturing the state of user-plane functions, edge compute resources, transport paths, and traffic dynamics. Unlike static analytical models, the DT integrates real-time telemetry with predictive modeling to support closed-loop control and proactive orchestration. Its primary role is to supply the control plane with accurate, timely, and actionable information that enables efficient power consumption estimation for each networked device.

At the core of the proposed DT is a persistent digital replica of the device in terms of CPU utilization, network

traffic and power consumption. This replica maintains detailed information on the status of networked devices and the operational state of UPF instances and other devices. The DT continuously receives telemetry data from distributed monitoring agents, including metrics related to latency, throughput, queue occupancy, compute load, and energy consumption. These measurements are fused into a coherent global view that reflects both instantaneous conditions and longer-term trends.

The continuous nature of this representation is essential for adapting to the heterogeneity of hardware platform and virtualization strategies employed in modern and future networks. By maintaining an up-to-date model of the system, the DT enables the control plane to reason about the feasibility of routing decisions, the availability of compute resources, and the expected impact of UPF placement or scaling actions having a precise knowledge of the existing trade-off between computation, networking and resource consumption characteristics of the specific devices that constitute the network.

A. The Digital Twin model

This section presents the Digital Twin (DT) framework for networked devices, that acts as an intelligent and continuously updated representation of operational network infrastructure. The DT integrates telemetry, predictive modeling, and machine learning to estimate power consumption and support proactive orchestration decisions.

The architecture monitors compute resources, network traffic, latency, throughput, queue occupancy, and energy consumption in real time. These measurements are fused into a global operational view that allows the control plane to optimize routing, UPF placement, scaling, and energy efficiency.

The proposed DT has three primary goals:

- Maintain a persistent and accurate digital representation of networked devices.
- Predict future workload and energy consumption trends.
- Enable closed-loop orchestration and energy-aware decision making.

In the case considered in this paper, the DT is especially focused on estimating the power consumption of devices as a function of CPU utilization and network traffic conditions.

The proposed DT combines real-time monitoring with forecasting models capable of anticipating future resource usage and bottlenecks. This predictive capability supports proactive UPF orchestration decisions such as: (i) instantiating new UPF instances; (ii) migrating workloads; (iii) consolidating resources; (iv) deactivating underutilized components.

The system therefore is capable of reacting before performance degradation occurs.

B. Mathematical Modeling

The system is modeled as a nonlinear dynamical system with hidden operational states and observed telemetry variables.

The Digital Twin approximates the workload-to-power mapping through a learned nonlinear operator:

Fig. 2. The diagram describing the implementation of the Digital Twin for Networked Devices

$$\mathcal{G}_{\Theta} : \mathbb{R}^{L \times d} \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \quad (1)$$

where:

$$\mathbf{X}_t \mapsto \hat{P}_t^{PC} \quad (2)$$

The power model includes:

- Baseline power,
- CPU-related power,
- Network-related power,
- Interaction effects between compute and communication workloads.

The framework also introduces temporal difference features and workload acceleration metrics to improve sensitivity to rapid workload changes.

The Transformer component learns global temporal and feature-level dependencies, while the BiLSTM component learns sequential memory and delayed workload effects. The dense regression head maps the learned representation to the monitored power output.

The complete implementation of the Digital Twin is described in the following Figure.

V. EVALUATION FRAMEWORK

This section introduces the framework used to evaluate the proposed architecture and its DT-driven orchestration mechanisms. Building on the control-loop principles described in Section VI, the objective of this evaluation is to discuss the benefits of predictive network intelligence for user-plane management, multimedia performance, and energy efficiency. The framework gives an insight of the interaction between the various components, that enable the systematic assessment of how dynamic UPF selection and data-plane adaptation influence end-to-end service behavior.

The evaluation focuses on a scenario representative of hypothetical workloads, characterized by stringent latency requirements, fluctuating traffic patterns, and heterogeneous compute demands. By examining these scenarios under controlled yet realistic conditions, we aim to provide useful

Fig. 3. Actual data collected from a Lenovo Thinkpad W540 laptop and on the right the data from the respective NDT

Fig. 4. Actual data collected from a Edgecore DCS201 AS5835-54X packet broker and on the right the data from the respective NDT

input for evaluating the effectiveness of the DT in guiding orchestration decisions and maintaining sustainable operation across the Compute Continuum.

Figures 3 and 4 provides an example of the resulting response surface provided by Digital Twins of two different networked devices: a Lenovo Thinkpad W540 laptop and an Edgecore DCS201 AS5835-54X packet broker. As expected, the corresponding response surfaces are different due to the different hardware architectures.

VI. EMERGING SEMANTIC-DRIVEN PARADIGMS IN NETWORK DIGITAL TWIN DESIGN

For upcoming multimedia use cases, goal-oriented and, more in general, semantic communications stand out as a promising 6G paradigm [11], enabling context-aware and task-driven multimedia delivery. Unlike conventional communication systems that treat all transmitted bits with equal importance, semantic communication introduces task-aware information prioritization, where only contextually relevant and decision-critical information is transmitted according to application intent, network conditions, and end-task requirements, enabling adaptive multimedia delivery with significantly lower communication and computation overhead, a rapidly emerging research topic in next-generation networks [12].

The (N)DTs provide the analytical foundation for enabling such semantic-aware orchestration. By continuously maintaining a synchronized virtual representation of the network and devices, semantic-aware (N)DTs can incorporate contextual information such as application intent, user perception, scene importance, and service relevance into the decision-making

process. This enables predictive adaptation, semantic QoE optimization, and proactive resource allocation under highly dynamic network conditions.

(N)DT capabilities extend also into the Radio Access Network (RAN) as well, particularly in architectures aligned with O-RAN principles [13]. In such systems, distributed intelligence is deployed throughout the RAN and the edge infrastructure, enabling more adaptive and efficient operation. Robust RAN control and optimization are critical for next-generation multimedia services, as it enables fine-grained, near-real-time orchestration of radio resources to meet stringent latency and reliability demands.

Within the O-RAN ecosystem, (N)DTs can provide to the O-RAN near-real-time control functions responsible for optimizing RAN operations. Unlike direct AI orchestration approaches, where AI models immediately trigger network actions, (N)DTs can be used in this context to first simulate and validate the impact of candidate actions on the RAN KPIs (QoS, QoE, and energy efficiency) before forwarding optimized control policies for actuation.

The (N)DT also provides semantic feature vectors that can be integrated into emerging semantic communication pipelines, allowing encoders and inference engines to adjust to real-time network conditions. This capability is particularly relevant in O-RAN-based deployments, where high multimedia load can affect both control and data planes. By supplying predictive insights at fine temporal granularity, the NDT enhances the responsiveness and robustness of distributed control loops. In the future, semantic-aware NDT systems will be extended to support multi-layer semantic hierarchies spanning application, network, compute, and energy semantics.

Despite the significant potential of a semantic-based (N)DT architecture, several open research challenges remain unresolved. One major challenge is semantic state representation, where large-scale and heterogeneous multi-domain telemetry collected from the RAN, edge, core, compute infrastructure, and applications must be intelligently abstracted into compact, meaningful, and task-oriented semantic representations suitable for near-real-time orchestration. Another critical challenge involves real-time synchronization between the physical network and distributed (N)DT instances. Scalability also has a relevant role, as multiple localized (N)DTs continuously exchange telemetry, semantic states, and prediction updates across large-scale 6G infrastructures. Finally, future multimedia systems require semantic-aware QoE metrics capable of jointly evaluating perceptual quality, contextual relevance, and task success beyond conventional QoS measurements [14]. Consequently, future semantic-aware multimedia systems must incorporate new evaluation frameworks capable of measuring semantic fidelity, inference accuracy, contextual importance, user perception, and successful completion of application-specific tasks under dynamic network conditions.

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper examined how Network Digital Twins can support next-generation multimedia services by enabling pre-

dictive, fine-grained orchestration across the communication–compute continuum. As workloads become more interactive and resource-intensive, static user-plane configurations are insufficient. The proposed architecture leverages continuous network-state awareness—including CPU load, link utilization, and power consumption—to guide dynamic UPF selection, energy-aware routing, and adaptive compute activation. Overall, the results indicate that NDT-driven orchestration is a key enabler for future 6G multimedia applications, supporting both performance and sustainability objectives. Future work will explore deeper integration with AI-native control and semantic communication frameworks.

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